

EVALUATING FACTORS AFFECTING THE ADOPTION OF MOBILE COMMERCE IN AGRICULTURE: SPECIAL REFERENCE TO GALAGEDARA AGA DIVISION.

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Introduction

Background of the research study

Every single meal one eats today is a result of Agricultural Revolution and Technological Revolution, which changed the attitudes of producers of agricultural products and Consumers. For Sri Lankans mobile devices are very user friendly and have been the fastest adopted consumer products with the more mobile phones than automobiles and Pcs. Mobile Commerce (m-commerce) refers to any direct or indirect transaction with monetary value conducted and facilitated through a wireless telecommunication network (Lee et al., 2007; Nagai & Gunasekaran, 2007). According to this research simply it will be studied whether m-commerce is the buying, selling of goods, and access to services and accumulate knowledge through wireless handheld devices such as smartphones and tablets by using internet.

Problem statement

According to the statistics recorded in Department of Census and Statistics, in 2016 Sri Lanka could be identified as a country with 23.7 million mobile subscriptions (113.4%). This is creating an opportunity for the growth of agriculture sector through m-commerce. That is by allowing to understand how farmer community make use mobile commerce. There are so many researchers all around the world who conducted the researches about adoption of mobile commerce in many areas. Aker J. C. (2011), Gilham, and Belle, (2005), Li, Fu, and Li, (2007) have done research about adoption

of mobile commerce in agriculture. Statistics show that there is a decline trend in the participation to the GDP by agricultural sector in Sri Lanka. This has been evident in Central Bank reports and census and statistics department reports (Central bank report 2017, 2019). In Sri Lankan context, there were limited number of researches done on adoption of mobile commerce in agriculture in Sri Lanka. Galagedara is an urban area where people have adopted to use m-commerce recently and shows significant spreading of agricultural lands which sustain both local market and foreign market specially by providing Cloves, Pepper and Cinnamon like spices. This study tried to fill up the identified gap in literature related to Sri Lanka, while concerning the evaluating factors affecting the adoption of mobile commerce in agriculture using special reference to Galagedara AGA division when it comes to the Sri Lankan context.

Research Objectives

In this study following objectives are intended to be achieved,

- I. To identify the factors affecting on the adoption of mobile commerce in agriculture in Galagedara. This study was limited to this area due to financial and time constrains.
- II. To determine how these factors influenced on agriculture in Galagedara.

Methodology

Many researchers have created models in line with the TAM of Davis to carry out their studies preferably. The model of (Li, Fu & Li, 2007) is selected to operationalize this study.

Hypotheses

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

H1: Compatibility will positively influence with attitudes to the adoption of m-commerce.

H2: Personal innovativeness will positively influence with attitudes to the adoption of m-commerce.

H3: Perceived ease of use (PEOU) will have a positive influence with the adoption of m-commerce.

H4: Perceived usefulness (PU) will have a positive influence with the adoption of m-commerce.

H5: Perceived reliability will positively influence with attitudes to the adoption of m-commerce.

H6: Cost will negatively influence attitudes to the adoption of m-commerce.

Design of the Study

This study is a quantitative cross sectional empirical research approach.

Population and Sample

The study population of the research is Sri Lankan Farmers. As the population is very large, Sample of Farmers from Galagedara AGA division were selected by convenient sampling method for this research. According to ex-ante power analysis the minimum Sample size is calculated as 103 Farmers. They are mainly paddy, peasant vegetable cultivators and pepper, cloves, cardamom like spices cultivators.

Operationalization

In the operationalization, each construct will be measured by using the questionnaire items in the previous researches.

Data Analysis Methods and Tools

Quantitative research study must analyse the responses that are collected from respondents. In here all information gathered from the questionnaires were analysed by using Smart PLS software.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Data analysis

Based on the responses collected out of 103 respondents, 100% respondents use mobile phones. However, when it comes to the Internet accessing among them, there are only 65 respondents (63.1%) out of the sample only. Although number of female Farmers who use phones among respondents

are significantly low 20 (19.4%) rather than male Farmers 83 (80.6%), but when it comes to the Internet accessing percentage of males are 52 (62.7%) while female Farmers' percentage is 13 (65%) from the sample.

Reliability and Validity Analysis

All the items loadings, all Cronbach's Alpha and Composite reliability values are greater than 0.7 as suggested by Hair et al. (2011) and thus the indicator reliability and internal consistency was established (Hair et al., 2011).

As suggested by Hair et al. (2011), all the AVE values are greater than 0.5 and thus Convergent validity was demonstrated (Hair et al., 2011).

None of the constructs' cross-correlations exceeded the respective square root of each construct's AVE, thus discriminant validity was demonstrated.

Hypothesis Testing

Each hypothesis was analysed and checked in relation to its relationship, path coefficient, T statistics and P- values in this study. Further, they categorized under supported and unsupported based on having P-value above 0.05 which was taken based on 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error.

The study could identify that, Compatibility positively and significantly influence Attitudes to m-commerce adoption ($P < 0.05, 0.000$). Personal innovativeness negatively influences attitudes to m-commerce adoption ($P < 0.05, 0.452$). Perceived ease of use (PEOU) positively influences attitudes to m-commerce adoption ($P < 0.05, 0.005$). Perceived usefulness (PU) negatively influences attitudes to m-commerce adoption ($P < 0.05, 0.076$). Perceived reliability negatively influences attitudes to m-commerce adoption ($P < 0.05, 0.309$). Cost positively and significantly influences to Attitudes to m-commerce adoption ($P < 0.05, 0.001$).

Findings and Conclusions

Table 2: Summary of the Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	Path	Path coefficient	T value	P value	Results
H1	Compatibility > Attitudes to m-commerce adoption	0.652	3.363	0.000	Supported
H2	Personal innovativeness > Attitudes to m-commerce adoption	0.057	0.753	0.452	Unsupported
H3	Perceived ease of use (PEOU) > Attitudes to m-commerce adoption	-0.389	2.827	0.005	Supported
H4	Perceived usefulness (PU) > Attitudes to m-commerce adoption	0.314	1.778	0.076	Unsupported
H5	Perceived reliability > Attitudes to m-	-0.121	1.018	0.309	Unsupported

	commerce adoption				
H6	Cost > Attitudes to m-commerce adoption	-0.397	3.363	0.001	Supported

Limitations

The questionnaire survey was conducted among the Farmers and there may be many factors that can affect the respondent's perception such as physical or mental conditions, stress, confidence level etc. which are different from each respondent to respondent. The days which survey were conducted were with slight drought condition in environment and there were some irrigation problems to supply water for their agricultural lands. Therefore, some of them were suffering lot by that time because for some their meals totally depend on that. Not only that group of farmers agricultural lands had got devastated by different diseases which were caused by harmful insects, fungus and that they had to burn those in the field observations. According to the field observations, another factor that makes them suffer are the harming by wild animals.

Recommendations

To achieve the objective of developing Farming in country there should be separate data bases to each district at least with the spatial differentiation of Farmers perceiving about the adoption of m-commerce. It is really better to have a collection of information about each AGA Division as this study to develop agriculture rapidly by using m-commerce. Thus, the Government also can empower the researches regarding this topic which can be conducted in different areas in the country. Further, to have highest outcome from that the officers also should apply the findings in real world practically too.

References

Aker J. C. (2011), 'Dial "A" for agriculture: a review of information and communication technologies for agricultural extension in developing countries. *Agricultural Economics*, 42(6), pp. 631-647.

Central Bank of Sri Lanka (2020) *Annual Report 2019*. Available at: <https://www.cbsl.gov.lk/en/publications/economic-and-financial-reports/annual-reports/annual-report-2019> (Accessed: 19 April 2020).

Central Bank of Sri Lanka (2020) *Annual Report 2017*. Available at: <https://www.cbsl.gov.lk/en/publications/economic-and-financial-reports/annual-reports/annual-report-2017> (Accessed: 19 April 2020).

Gilham, C. and Van Belle, J.P. (2005), 'Factors Affecting the Adoption of Mobile Content Services amongst Youth in the Western Cape, South Africa'. *Proceedings of the 4th International Business Information Management Conference*.

Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M. and Sarstedt, M. (2011), 'PLS-SEM : Indeed a Silver Bullet', *Journal of Marketing theory and Practice*, 19(2), pp. 139–151.

Lee, C., Kenneth, H. and Cheng, H. (2007), 'An empirical study of mobile commerce in insurance industry: Task – technology fit and individual differences', *Decision support systems*, 43(1), pp. 95–110.

Li, Y., Fu, Z. T. and Li, H. (2007), 'Evaluating factors affecting the adoption of mobile commerce in agriculture: An empirical study',

New Zealand Journal of Agricultural Research, 50(5), pp. 1213-1218.

Ngai, E. W. T. And Gunasekaran, A. (2007), 'A review for mobile commerce research and applications', *Decision support systems*,43(1), pp. 3–15.

Statista (2020) Number of mobile cellular subscriptions in Sri Lanka from 2000 to 2019. Available at:

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/501125/number-of-mobile-cellular-subscriptions-in-sri-lanka> (Accessed: 6 April 2020).